

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar Regions and Beyond

Thomas Jung (Coordinator)
Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727862.

Mission

Develop enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond, and

Determine the influence of Arctic climate change on Northern Hemisphere mid-latitudes ...

For the benefit of policy makers, businesses and society

Some facts

Consortium → 17 partners • 9 countries • many collaborators

Budget → 8 Mio € • separate Russian contribution

Duration → 1st November 2016–1st April 2021

APPLICATE Kick-off, AWI, January 2017

Establishing the status quo

CMIP6 sea ice projections

Arctic sea ice extent (September)

Antarctic sea ice extent (January)

High-resolution climate modelling

Resolution: 1/2 of the Rossby radius of deformation capped at 4km (8km) in the Northern Hemisphere (Southern Hemisphere)

High-resolution climate modelling

High-resolution climate modelling

Displayed on a common $1/4^\circ$ mesh

High-resolution climate modelling

HiResMIP Projections (RCP 8.5): 2070–2099 minus 1976–2005

High-resolution sea ice-ocean modelling

Global mesh with 1km Arctic

High-resolution sea ice-ocean modelling

Relative vorticity at 250m depth

FESOM2
Finite volume
Sea Ice-Ocean Model

Arctic-midlatitude linkages

North American cold snaps

Weather, News

Meteorologists believe yesterday was Montreal's coldest snowstorm in nearly a century

 Tyler Jadah
Jan 21, 2019 6:54 am 🔥 139

European heat waves

Divergent consensus...

Link between AA and severe winter weather?

Arctic-midlatitude linkages

The jet stream – Dynamical driver of extreme events

A coordinate approach (CMIP6-PAMIP)

Geosci. Model Dev., 12, 1139–1164, 2019
https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-1139-2019
© Author(s) 2019. This work is distributed under
the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

GMD | Articles | Volume 12, issue 3

Article

Assets

Peer review

Metrics

Related articles

Model experiment description paper

25 Mar 2019

The Polar Amplification Model Intercomparison Project (PAMIP) contribution to CMIP6: investigating the causes and consequences of polar amplification

Doug M. Smith¹, James A. Screen², Clara Deser³, Judah Cohen⁴, John C. Fyfe⁵, Javier García-Serrano^{6,7}, Thomas Jung^{8,9}, Vladimir Kattsov¹⁰, Daniela Matej¹¹, Rym Msadek¹², Yannick Peings¹³, Michael Sigmond⁵, Jinro Ukita¹⁴, Jin-Ho Yoon¹⁵, and Xiangdong Zhang¹⁶

¹Met Office Hadley Centre, Exeter, UK

²College of Engineering, Mathematics and Physical Sciences, University of Exeter, Exeter, UK

³Climate and Global Dynamics, National Center for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, CO, USA

⁴Atmospheric and Environmental Research, Lexington, MA, USA

⁵Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis, Environment and Climate Change Canada, Victoria, British Columbia, Canada

⁶Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Barcelona, Spain

⁷Group of Meteorology, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

⁸Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, Germany

⁹Institute of Environmental Physics, University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany

¹⁰Voeikov Main Geophysical Observatory, Roshydromet, St. Petersburg, Russia

¹¹Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie, Hamburg, Germany

¹²CERFACS/CNRS, UMR 5318, Toulouse, France

¹³Department of Earth System Science, University of California Irvine, Irvine, CA, USA

¹⁴Institute of Science and Technology, Niigata University, Niigata, Japan

¹⁵Gwangju Institute of Science and Technology, School of Earth Sciences and Environmental Engineering, Gwangju, South Korea

¹⁶International Arctic Research Center, University of Alaska Fairbanks, Fairbanks, AK, USA

Response to future sea ice loss

- ★ Atmosphere simulations completed by 15 models from APPLICATE and international community
- ★ Robust weakening and equatorward shift of tropospheric jet
- ★ Stratosphere response not robust
- ★ Model spread – to be understood

Response to future sea ice loss

Does resolution make a difference?

Opportunity and challenge

FEATURE 10 October 2018

Could the world's mightiest computers be too complicated to use?

China, Japan and the US are racing to build the first exascale computer – but devising programmes clever enough to run on them is a different story

Totto Renna

- End of Moore's law
- End of Dennard scaling
- New and heterogeneous architectures
- Truly "big data"

www.extremearth.eu

Climate modelling in polar regions

- Despite of recent progress substantial biases remain
- These model short-comings matter (e.g. Antarctic sea ice paradox)
- Rapid progress is needed to inform decision makers (beyond incremental)
 - Pushing the boundaries of resolution is very promising (more physics)
 - „Pictures“ of the future (also storyline scenarios)
 - Exascale computing → Opportunities and challenges (we have a concept ExtremeEarth)

Impact of Arctic climate change on mid-latitude weather and climate

- Rapidly moving field (PAMIP) → Quantitative knowledge within reach through further investments in research

Arctic ocean ocean and wind biases

SLP bias AWI-CM

T@400m: ERA-I
1980–1988

T@400m: ERA-I + wind bias
1980–1988

Antarctic sea ice paradox

Antarctic sea ice paradox

Establishing the status quo

CMIP6-SIMIP sea ice budget

Keen et al. 2019 (submitted)
Notz et al. 2019 (submitted)

Response to future sea ice loss

How many ensemble members?

- ★ 200 members at least to detect a significant response in the stratosphere

Deliver enhanced predictions across time scales

